

METHODOLOGY-AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THE STUDY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The purpose of this scientific article is the role of methodology in learning foreign languages, the impact of different methods on learners. To be able to use them widely in the language, in the lesson, about the important rules of language learning in our modern life, especially in the life of young people. And of course, about teachers working on themselves.*

Keywords: *methodology, methods, approaches, teaching foreign languages, teaching environment, language abilities, internet platforms, skills.*

Introduction: Methodology - it is one of the most important factors in the process of language learning and teaching. Effective use of additional resources in teaching foreign languages to students, further increase their interest and attitude to foreign language with the help of auxiliary teaching tools, conduct each lesson in interactive, that is, active-student methods, give them additional classes after classes, and widely use unconventional methods in this process.

The term "method" refers to the acquisition of knowledge, skills, on the way to create worldview, formation and knowledge opportunities in students means the working method of a teacher-pedagogue and a language learner or student. That's why this concept is number -has countless definitions.

It should be mentioned that, the methodology of teaching and learning a foreign language did not appear today or yesterday. It has a very long history. In ancient times, all peoples traded with each other and had to learn each other's languages for trade. If merchants know the language of a foreign country well, it is very necessary for their goods to be sold more. Later, the study of foreign languages was widely developed, so that they could freely talk with the heads of those states, other heads of states or kingdoms. And in turn, the methods of learning foreign languages were developed by the scientists of that time. That's why language learning methods have been effective for centuries. Even today, without losing its validity, it is still improving. These days, knowledge of a foreign language is very important for representatives of all fields. Because many of the news and innovations coming from abroad, techniques and other types of household tools, for us to learn how to use them correctly, it is very important to know the language in it. That's why language learning and teaching centers have increased a lot than recent years. Language learning has always been considered one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, is formed in the natural environment, that is, in the family, and among the public or it can be acquired practically in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is theoretical is taught in terms of Knowledge of languages in our era, when international relations and business cooperation are on the rise, multilingualism is especially important. Hence the need to study it never fades.

The process of learning a language is sometimes difficult for people, and sometimes easy. The reason for this can be different. But one of the important reasons may be that they are learning this language using the wrong technique or the wrong method. How can we behave in such

situations, what is the importance of methodology in language learning, we will consider it now. The role of psychology in foreign language teaching methodology.

In my opinion, psychology also has its place in this process. Because a teacher should be able to be a psychologist first of all. Let's say you come to a group, and if you only work with the excellent ones all the time, and don't pay attention to a kid sitting in the back or in the corner, then you're going to have some help in this area with great ability. Because it is a psychological process, the fact that you can work with those shy students, as a teacher, you should attract them to the lesson is also a method and a psychological process that takes place during it. Sometimes such shy learners are actually the most powerful knowledge holders. It's just that they can't show off their skills in front of everyone. That is, you should choose a suitable methodology based on the psychology and nature of each language learner. The ability of the teacher as a motivator, to attract students to the language learning process, to encourage them, to motivate them, is also considered a psychological process. And even here, different methods are used.

Language learning methods should be different for learners of different ages.

Communication in a foreign language is mainly under the guidance of the teacher will pass. Because his role is like a guide in this process. And this, in turn, the appropriate foreign language teaching technology, methods, concepts require application. Thorough mastering of the achievements of the foreign language teacher methodical science to clearly know the standard of the language experience of the student and further it achieves improvement. In such situations as effective teaching of foreign languages, its practical application, assimilation into the minds of others, it is necessary to know its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages is in many ways foreign language teaching development of methodological issues from the theoretical side and theory in practice depends on the creative application.

For younger learners, appropriate methods and strategies can be used. Let's say that if the language learning process is organized for them through pictures, or through toys, or through various games, it will be very interesting and at the same time memorable for them. Some children learn the language quickly when they see a cartoon in a foreign language, that is, they have a strong visual learning style. Even if they are given tasks in the form of role play, they do it sincerely based on their interests. In such cases, it is effective for teachers to conduct lessons using methods that suit them.

For adult learners, it is better to use methods and strategies suitable for them in the process of learning foreign languages, based on their fields. For example, people who work in radio or music have a very high hearing ability. And for them, learning by listening is very suitable. Besides that, there are such professions, for instance, people who work in the field of logistics, or people who work in the field that always uses their brains, this process will be very effective for them if they learn foreign languages through using various quizzes, puzzles, logic games, vocabulary games. So that, I think the learners will be able to learn the language more deeply if they are use the methods related to their fields or their skills.

It should be noted separately that in traditional pedagogy, the use of such types as Brain storming, cluster, project, method as specific methods of innovative technology gives great results. In some cases, many believe that a language cannot be spoken unless it is grammar-conscious, and their main time is spent on the perfect study of grammatic. However, the level of intellectual potential, acquisition, acceptance, awareness and memory will be developed in each student in a special way. Someone receives well by hearing, writing or reading, and someone else only by

seeing and speaking. Therefore, each student should be approached individually, based on his potential, and most importantly, we also need to make the most of the methods of developing oral speech. A student who sets himself the goal of learning a foreign language perfectly should, first of all, master his native language perfectly in all respects. Because if the learner does not know his native language perfectly, he cannot translate a word or phrase in a foreign language.

And below I would like to cite some of the innovative educational methods and technologies that I support in my activities in teaching a foreign language and give positive results.

The purpose of oral speech training is to recall words, phrases, samples raised by the memory of students, listen in the foreign language that they are learning, prepare speech organs for speaking. Let's say in some English lesson, showing a picture, asking in English what he sees and who or what is in the picture, telling them to write a short essay about the situation, and more ways to ask additional questions to express their thoughts after use, which oral speech begins to form in them. While some lessons begin with speaking foreign languages, so students are in the same environment throughout the lesson. This environment is the main factor for them to learn this language faster. In this process, of course, the ability to listen and understand and speak also develops.

If the language learners like the culture, customs, food, or products of the foreign country they are studying, watch a video or movie with them about these topics, analyze it in depth, and say them tell it again. So, in such cases, the "retelling" method is also effective.

The use of the "Brain storming" method also gives itself a great result and effect.

In this, a "mental attack" is organized on students, the first events of an event are read in English, and students are required to continue it logically. Of course, during the use of these modern methods of teaching, it is advisable for the teacher to correct every grammatical, lexical, orthographic and other errors and shortcomings of students in their place. This method is very interesting for every student, who unknowingly try to use all the words they know in the foreign language they are learning. For example, I use this method extensively in my English lessons. In one lesson, I give them a short beginning of the fairy tale "Little Red Riding Hood", that is, I ask them to continue the events, in an unusual case, based on their own. For them, this process is interesting and at the same time allows to listen to the ideas of each participant, his speech, pronunciation.

Through the use of these types of mixed and pure lessons, students are able to speak English, listen and understand, develop reading, writing, memory and logical thinking, raise their level and spirituality of knowledge, form mental labor skills, as well as develop the mental, emotional and motivational characteristics of the student's personality.

Conclusion: As we know today, there are very many qualified young people who speak foreign languages. In addition, due to the development of times, many young people are learning foreign languages through different sites or internet platforms. Perhaps that is why today's youth in old methods or simple teaching is somehow boring for them, based on their interests, each teacher should develop his own teaching method. Language learning is a complex and exciting process. And it is very important to carry it together in the learning process, not forgetting the very important role of methodology. Therefore, in order to further develop these works, all foreign language teachers need to tirelessly work on themselves, enrich their skills in research, practical and theoretical. They need to keep up with the Times, use modern innovative educational technologies during classes.

However, going abroad is not as complicated or difficult as it was in the past. therefore, if teachers want to improve their skills, they can be sent abroad for training by the enterprises or organizations they work for. This is also mainly important, because through such exchange programs, teachers can further improve their knowledge and skills, study foreign methods more deeply and when they return to their countries, they teach or share them with other professionals. The need to learn a language is increasing day by day, so I think it is very important to teach it, to divide it into different methods and to teach it in practice.

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